

CARE₄DAIRY

Mini-review

Cattle fitness for transport

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1. The issue

Transport is considered to be a significant stressor in ruminants (Hong et al, 2019). The ability to cope with loading and unloading, food and water restriction, mixing with unfamiliar animals, vehicle motion during the journey and exposure to novel environments, can be challenging even for fit and healthy cattle (Eicher et al., 2001; Bulitta et al., 2015).

The assessment of fitness for transport is a significant factor in determining adequate animal well-being, food safety and economic outcomes of the transportation. The European legislation states that '*all animals shall be transported in conditions guaranteed not to cause them injury or unnecessary suffering*'. However, animals transported with pre-existing conditions such as lameness, mastitis, or general weakness are more likely to die in transit, become non-ambulatory or be euthanised on arrival, compared to those that are healthy (Cockram, 2019).

The fitness of dairy cows for transport is mainly determined by management practices at farm level. Identification and treatment of medical conditions, health disorders, injuries or poor body condition, as well as decisions relating to culling, prior to deterioration of health status, have a huge impact on overall cow fitness (Cockram, 2021). In addition, the duration and season of transportation have been shown to affect cows' fitness for transport, where cows removed from dairy farms in certain months (notably during summer and autumn) were more likely to have poor fitness (Stojkov et al., 2020).

Calves are more vulnerable during transport due to the immaturity of their immune system and reduced thermoregulating ability (Bernardini et al., 2012). Umbilical infections and calf age are the main reasons they are assessed as unfit for transport and at higher risk of mortality. The welfare of male dairy calves is often compromised because they are usually transported at a younger age than beef calves. Moreover, their fitness to transport is overlooked as a consequence of their low economic value (Rocarro et al., 2022).

2. Legal requirements

2.1. Council Regulation No 1/2005 on the protection of animals during transport and related operations

Within the European Union, Council Regulation No 1/2005 defines general conditions and requirements for the transport of animals. The Regulation establishes two types of requirements regarding fitness for transport: *a) animals must be fit for the journey, b) in the case of long journeys, competent authorities and official veterinarians must perform checks for fitness on loading and unloading points*. Although Member States have started to report explicitly on compliance with these rules, since 2014, it is highlighted that the definition of the term «fitness» seems still to be problematic for all the involved

stakeholders. Practical and economic considerations lead to situations where inspections are not performed properly, and animals are declared fit when they are not.

EU regulation contains no specific rules regarding cull cows. A list of medical conditions resulting in animals being deemed unfit for transport, may also be relevant for cull dairy cows. More specifically, it is stated that *animals that are unable to move independently without pain or walk unassisted; animals with a severe open wound or prolapse; animals in the last tenth of pregnancy or animals that have given birth in the previous week* are considered unfit for transfer. Additionally, it is suggested that *lactating animals transported without their offspring must be milked at intervals of no longer than 12 hours*.

Unweaned calves will require consideration of their age and healing of the navel. It is stated that *calves cannot be transported if their navel has not completely healed*. Moreover, *calves of less than 10 days of age cannot be transported for more than 100 km and for journeys that exceed 8h they must be older than 14 days*. This assessment can however be difficult, as the term «healed» remains ambiguous and authorities rely on farmers' declarations regarding the reported date of birth. Most hazards threatening compliance with the rules arise for journeys over 100km, where: evaluation of equipment, clinical condition of the animal prior to transport, and provision of feeding, drinking and resting intervals, must all be adequate.

2.2. Guide to good practices for the transport of cattle

Within the framework of the Animal Transport Guides project, welfare risks and recommendations relating to fitness for transport for all cattle types are described. Guidelines for criteria supporting fitness or unfitness and restrictions for transport are presented on Annex 1.

3. Summary of the scientific knowledge¹

3.1. Dairy cows

Studies relevant to fitness have often focused on transport conditions in pigs and beef cattle, categorising them as either fit or with reduced health (Thomson et al., 2015; Fogsgaard et al., 2018). However, it seems reasonable that dairy cows are more vulnerable to stress associated with transport, when compared to other types of cattle, because the reason for their culling and transport is often ill health, such as mastitis or lameness (Nielsen et al., 2011). There is a notable scarcity of research data regarding the concept of fitness for dairy cows, compared to other species. Published studies considering this welfare concern are presented below.

¹ The scientific reviews prepared for CARE4DAIRY focused on the literature of the last 10 years, assuming that older articles have already been taken into account in current technical recommendations. Older articles may be cited if they provide complementary knowledge.

The concept of fitness for dairy cows emerged 30 years ago in the United States. From 1993 to 1999, the percentage of dairy cows arriving with arthritic leg joints at slaughter plants had tripled (Grandin et al., 2001). Edwards-Callaway et al. (2019), noted that although many guidelines and recommendations are provided to the dairy industry, cull dairy cows still face a lot of welfare challenges, as none of the recommendations were mandatory.

There are a few studies providing evidence that dairy cows arriving at abattoirs did not satisfy fitness criteria. Nicholson et al. (2013), in an in-plant survey conducted in the USA, which to quantified transportation management practices in the beef processing sector, observed that 37% of cows had a visible defect (e.g. foot abnormalities, extreme emaciation, abscesses) during visual appraisal. In addition, almost half of them received a locomotion score of 2 or above (using a 5-point scoring system, described by Zinpro performance minerals, 2013), and 8.7% were affected by mastitis. Stojkov et al. (2020) described the clinical condition of 6,263 cull dairy cows sold at livestock markets in British Columbia. Slight to severe locomotion abnormalities were observed in 59.5% of the cows, while 6.8% received a high locomotion score ($LS \geq 4$ in a 5-point scale described by Flower and Weary, 2006). Quality defects were observed in 6.2% of the cows (abscesses, signs of disease or weakness, hobbles, signs of pneumonia, eye injury and lumpy jaw). Additionally, 11.9% were assigned a body condition score of 2 or less (using a 1-5 scale scoring system with 0.5 increments, described by Ferguson et al., 1994) and 3.0% had an udder inflammation. Similarly, Harris et al. (2017) quantified the condition of dairy cows at arrival to slaughter plants; 9% were extremely thin, 43% had a defect (swollen joint or foot abnormality) and 23% were mobility-challenged.

Those findings are in accordance with Sánchez-Hidalgo et al. (2019) and Dahl-Petersen et al. (2018b). The latter study investigated the deterioration of clinical condition using pre (on farm) and post transport (at unloading) assessment. New, or deterioration in, lameness was identified in 19% of cows. New wounds were identified in 12% of the cows (34% after versus. 22% before and milk leakage in an additional 16% (17% after vs. 1%).

3.2. Calves

Most studies considering fitness to travel for calves focus on navel condition in unweaned calves and age at transport. It is reported that the prevalence of navel inflammation at unloading ranges from 20% to 32% (Wilson et al., 2000; Pempek et al., 2017). Although the observed mortality rates at transport are low (Padalino et al., 2018), there is a strong negative correlation between age at transport and mortality. Mortality rates increase within a few weeks of transport, due to compromised immune systems and secondary infection following stress of transport (Roccaro et al., 2022).

Wilson et al. (2020) described the condition of male dairy calves arriving at auction markets. Twenty percent of calves had at one or more health disorders: navel disease (12%), ocular or nasal discharge (4%), a depressed (dull, unable, or unwilling to rise) attitude (2%), coughing (2%), and joint inflammation (1%). Similarly, Marquou et al.

(2019) reported omphalitis (swelling, discharge, or pain of the navel) as the most common abnormality (20.3% of calves).

4. Assessment of fitness for transport – *guidelines & indicators*

Evaluation of pre-transport physical state is necessary for the assessment of fitness. The presence of painful clinical conditions may be exacerbated by movement during transport. EFSA (2022) has published a list of conditions resulting in for cattle being deemed unfit for transport (Annex 2). Farmers, veterinarians and livestock drivers must be trained in recognising these conditions to ensure the fitness of those transported and to identify those who are not. The conditions most commonly presently and of greatest welfare concern are detailed below:

- **Lameness:** Lameness is one of the most prevalent health disorders in cows and constitutes a frequent reason for culling (Wilson et al., 2022). The severity of this condition should not be underestimated, as it can lead to reduced ability to walk in loading ramps, stand and maintain balance during transport.
- **Body condition score (BCS):** Romero et al. (2020) confirm that body condition of cull cows at the end of their productive life is often compromised and this is considered a key factor in assessment of fitness for transport. The evaluation guidelines were developed based on the recommendations of Welfare Quality (Welfare Quality, 2009). Cows with low BCS values (≤ 2) have compromised welfare and are anticipated to have more difficulty coping with the difficult conditions associated with transport (1-5 scale scoring system with 0.5 increments, described by Ferguson et al., 1994).
- **Udder inflammation:** Udder inflammation/ mastitis is one of the main reasons cows are considered unfit for transport. (Gradin et al., 2001). Mastitis is a painful condition which compromises animal welfare. In cases where mastitis is not present, but lactating animals have not been milked prior to transport, they may develop a swollen, painful udder. This may increase their reluctance to load/unload and cause discomfort when walking.
- **Navel condition:** Calves with completely healed and therefore sealed navels are considered fit for transport. A dried, shrivelled navel stump or the presence of granulation tissue (scab) covering the umbilical wound navel reduces the risk of ascending infection during transport. Navel sealing is not a reliable indicator of calf age, as it can be observed from day 1 to 60 (Roccaro et al., 2022).
- **Respiratory diseases:** There are a multitude of stressors associated with transport, resulting in immune suppression and increased vulnerability to respiratory diseases (Early et al., 2017). Compromised lungs result in reduced oxygen uptake, which becomes problematic when combined with the additional muscular activity required during handling and transportation (Lowie et al., 2022).

Bovine respiratory disease (BRD) is one of the main pathogens associated with this compromise and it can be recognised by identification of the 7 main visual signs: lethargy (slow to move in response to stimulus), head carriage, laboured breathing, cough, nasal discharge, ocular discharge, and rumen fill, with each sign assigned a score ranging from 0 to 3, with 3 being the most severe (Blakebrough-Hall et al.,2020).

5. Future directions and challenges

Better definition of the concept of “fitness for transport.” A consistent, universally agreed list of assessment criteria for “fitness for transport” should be developed and utilised across all EU countries.

Acceptable distance/duration of transport criteria. Identification and assessment of all the applicable risk factors should be evaluated in advance of planned transport and a decision made as to whether the journey plan is acceptable or considered to cause additional or unnecessary suffering.

Proper education and training of all stakeholders involved in transportation. In a survey of farmers (Dahl-Pedersen,2022) 1/3 of respondents reported doubt or lack of knowledge, at least sometimes, in recognising if an animal is unfit for transport. More than half of them reported that they at least sometimes found it difficult to interpret the rules. Concurrently, an agreement between the stakeholders (farmers, livestock drivers, veterinarians) regarding fitness assessment of “fitness to travel” has been utilized (Dahl-Pedersen, 2018a). Continuing education programs and training will be necessary to improve decision-making criteria for fitness to travel and ensure consistency between different professionals in their evaluation. Ensuring availability of both guidelines and learning resources for farmers will help to improve awareness for animal welfare and standardise the assessment procedures before animals are considered fit for travel.

Increase the role of the veterinary profession and competent in consultation/involvement in culling decision making.

Assessment of the severity of lameness. The implement of locomotion (Annex 3) and lameness (Annex 4) scoring systems is necessary for the assessment of fitness for transport in lame animals.

Preventative measures for udder inflammation. The treatment of clinical mastitis cases, respect for milk withdrawal periods, milking before transportation and utilization of dry-cow treatments should be considered obligatory.

Alternative options. Direct-to-slaughter, emergency slaughter and on farm-euthanasia for animals with compromised welfare should be considered as an alternative to routine transportation.

Genetic selection. Selection of animals with enhanced genetic resilience to stress may help to reduce the magnitude of this problem.

Financial incentives. Provision of adequate compensation for farmers whose dairy animals are unfit for transport, will help improve their adherence to animal welfare standard compliance.

6. Annexes

Annex 1. *Practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of adult bovines (adapted from Eurogroup for animals, UECBV, Animals' Angels, ELT, FVE, IRU, 2012)*

<u>Supporting criteria for fitness for transport</u>	
Attentiveness & responsiveness Shiny/dry hide, well groomed Normal breathing Good body condition Weight distribution on all 4 legs, straight back line No obvious signs of pain	
Cattle in poor condition	
Fit for transport under close supervision	Unfit for transport
Apathetic	Unable to stand up or remaining standing
Watery/dull eyes	Unable to move without pain (obviously lame, not distributing weight on all 4 legs, arched back, abnormal posture & gait, shallow frequent breathing)
Refusal to drink or eat	Unable to walk unassisted
Fever (>39,5°C) or hypothermia (< 37,5°C)	
Increased breathing frequency, panting, open- mouth breathing, coughing	
Signs of severe pain (arched back, shallow frequent breathing, abnormal posture or gait, heavy sweating without physical exercise or heat)	
Extreme thinness	

Annex 2. List of conditions that can make cattle unfit for transport (adapted from EFSA Journal, 2022)

General condition	Specific condition
Sickness/illness	Evidence of pathology: laboured breathing, congestive heart failure, generalised nervous system disorder, shock or dying, fever, pneumonia., unresponsive with fever, infected navel, gangrenous udder, acute mastitis, bloated to the extent that the animal exhibits signs of discomfort or weakness, purulent discharges, actinomycosis (lumpy jaw), extensive cancer/leukosis, ketosis, orchitis, swollen penis, abscesses, peritonitis, urinary calculi causing abdominal distention
Pathophysiological State	Weakness, emaciation, fatigue/exhaustion, dehydration, distress, hypothermia, hyperthermia, engorged udder
Eye lesion	Blind in both eyes, severe squamous cell carcinoma
Injuries	Severe open wound or a severe laceration, disabled/infirmity, unhealed wounds after recent surgery, severe haemorrhage, has sustained an injury and is hobbled to aid in treatment, ingrown horn, broken horns if bone tissue is affected or animal appears depressed
Prolapse	Prolapsed uterus or a severe rectal or severe vaginal prolapse
Hernia	Hernia that (i) impedes movement, including when a hind limb of the animal touches the hernia as the animal is walking, (ii) causes signs of pain or suffering, (iii) touches the ground when the animal is standing in its natural position, or (iv) has an open wound, ulceration or obvious infection
Experiencing pain	Cannot be moved/transported without causing additional suffering, experience pain when moving, fracture that impedes mobility or causes pain or suffering
Lameness	Unable to bear weight on each leg, lame in one or more limbs to extent that it exhibits signs of pain or suffering and halted movements or a reluctance to walk, unable to walk as fast as a brisk human pace (cannot keep up with the healthy herd) likely to lose balance during transport, arthritis in multiple joints
Reproductive stage	Pregnancy: Final 10% of gestation period, last month of pregnancy, within 2 weeks of calving
	Recent calving: Given birth within previous 48h to previous 14 days, visible placenta
New-born	Unhealed navel
	<1-week-old

Annex 3. Description of locomotion and traits score (adapted from Flower and Weary, 2006)

Level	Locomotion	Arched back	Asym-metric gait	Head bobbing	Reluctance to bear weight	Tracking up
1	Smooth and fluid movement	Flat back	Long and confident stride or step	Steady head carriage	All legs bear weight equally	Hind-limb hooves land on or in front of fore-limb hooves
2	Imperfect locomotion but ability to move freely not diminished	Mildly arched back	Slightly asymmetric gait	Slight head bobbing	Slight limp can be discerned	Hind-limb hooves and front hooves do not track up perfectly (approximately one hoof distance between track of front and hind-limb hooves)
3	Capable locomotion but ability to move freely is compromised	Arched back	Short strides or step	Head bobbing (associated with release of the affected limb from the floor)	Limp can be discerned	Hind-limb hooves do not track up (approximately 2 hooves distance between track of front and hind hooves)
4	Ability to move freely is obvious diminished	Obvious arched back	Short and hesitant strides or step	Obvious head bobbing (associated with release of the affected limb from the floor)	Clearly reluctant to bear weight on at least one limb but uses that limb in locomotion	Hind-limb hooves do not track up (approximately 3 hooves distance between track of front and hind-limb hooves)
5	Ability to move is severely restricted and must be vigorously encouraged to move	Exaggerated arched back	Very short, hesitant, and deliberate strides or step	Exaggerated head bobbing (associated with release of the affected limb from the floor)	Inability to bear weight on the limb or more than one limb clearly affected	Poor tracking up with short strides (approximately 4 or more hooves distance between track of front and hind-limb hooves)

Annex 4. Locomotion scoring system (Thomas et al., 2015)

Score	Description
0	Walks with even weight bearing and rhythm on all 4 feet, with a flat back. Long fluid strides possible.
1	Steps uneven (rhythm or weight bearing or strides shortened, affected limb or limbs not immediately identifiable).
2a	Mild asymmetry in hind-limb movement. Decreased stride length on affected limb and slightly decreased stance duration with a corresponding increase in limb flight velocity on the nonaffected side. Walking velocity remains normal. Back may be raised.
2b	Moderate asymmetry in hind-limb movement. Decreased stride length on affected limb and a distinct decrease in stance duration. Limb flight on the nonaffected limb is correspondingly faster and the overall walking velocity is reduced. Back usually raised.
3a	Severe asymmetry in hind-limb movement. Marked decrease in stride length on affected limb and very short stance duration. Limb flight on nonaffected limb rapid and walking velocity reduced such that cow cannot keep up with healthy herd. Back raised.
3b	Minimal or non-weight bearing on affected limb. Back raised. Reluctant to walk without encouragement.

Annex 5 presents a check list developed for the evaluation of pre-transport indicators for fitness assessment that takes into consideration all indicators mentioned above.

Annex 5. Evaluation of pre-transport indicators for fitness assessment

Indicator	Description	Check-list
Attentiveness & responsiveness	Normal	
	Apathetic	
	Unable to stand up	
Body condition	Normal	
	Extreme thinness	
Lameness	Arched back	
	Reluctance to walk	
	Lame in one limb	

	Lame in more limbs	
	Unable to walk un-assisted	
Breathing frequency	Normal	
	Increased	
	Panting	
	Open- mouth breathing	
	Coughing	
Reproductive/Physiological stage	Lactating	
	Dry period	
	Last month of pregnancy	
	Within 2 weeks of calving	
Newborn	Unhealed navel	
	<1-week-old	
Pathological conditions	None	
	Hypothermia/ hyperthermia	
	Prolapsed uterus or rectum	
	Injuries	
	Mastitis/engorged udder	
	Navel inflammation	
	Other	

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